

**BOSHLANG'ICH SINIF O'QUVCHILARIDA KREATIV TAFAKKURNI
TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MEXANIZMLARI**

(ingliz tilini o'rgatish misolida)

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Annotatsiya: *Mazkur maqolada bugungi kunda ingliz tilini o'qitishda boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida kreativ tafakkurni shakllantirish dolzarbligi va uni rivojlantirish maqsadida ingliz tili o'qituvchilarining foydalanishi lozim bo'lgan vazifalari haqidagi kerakli ma'lumotlar keltirib o'tilgan. Shuningdek, o'quvchilarni kreativ fikrlashga o'rgatishning afzalliklari haqida ham ma'lumotlar berilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilari, o'qituvchi, kreativ fikrlash, kreativ tafakkur, metod.*

Annotation: *In this article, the necessary information about the relevance of the formation of creative thinking in primary school students and the tasks that English teachers should use in order to develop it in the teaching of the English language today is presented. Information is also given about the benefits of teaching students to think creatively.*

Key words: *primary school students, teacher, creative thinking, method.*

Introduction

In the modern world, teaching any foreign language especially English language is highly increasing. Not only educational sphere, but other spheres are demanding to learn language. Teaching English language for primary school pupils is not easy for English language teachers. Moreover, teaching is not enough for them, they should be competitive and creative. Thinking is a higher-order cognitive activity taking place in the human psyche. Creative thinking is always associated with the creation of new things, is the process of human activities that create spiritual and new material values. Creative thinking is characterized by basic components, such as flexibility, fluency, originality, elaboration, and problem sensibility. In particular, the above characteristics of creative thinking are not separate from each other, but they are closely related and complement each other, in which originality is said to be the most important in creative expression, problem sensibility of problems associated with

the mechanism of creative appearance. Flexibility and fluency are the basis for being able to achieve originality, problem sensibility, elaboration and perfection.

Despite the importance of both content knowledge and creative thinking for educational and professional achievement, classroom instruction often provides few opportunities for students to think creatively. Nevertheless, creative thinking and problem solving can be built into instruction in many ways. For example, teachers can encourage students to seek out new connections between disparate ideas or ask students to offer multiple and varied solutions to complex problems. Ken Robinson said that if the ability to be creative is indeed vital for students' future success, teachers must explicitly foster and teach creativity in school. On this view, creativity training should be a key component of primary and secondary education. Nevertheless, creativity training only makes sense if we assume that everyone can think creatively and that creativity can be influenced. Fortunately, many researchers such as: Amabile, Kaufman, Beghetto have argued—and in some cases demonstrated empirically—that every individual possesses the ability to think creatively, at least within particular contexts. As mentioned Brophy further, research has shown that creative thinking is influenced by various circumstances, including whether work is collaborative and the extent to which individuals are motivated to solve a problem. DeHaan explained that these findings support the idea that creativity is pliable and that creative thinking can and should be taught in some way.[1]

Creative thinking plays an important role, especially at the primary school level. Creative thinking is a key factor for learners to develop problem-solving abilities in real life. The formation and development of creative thinking competence are to help learners have the habit of not only independent thinking moreover, creating new and unique ideas with high efficiency in problem-solving. In teaching at primary school, the training of creative thinking for students is considered to play an important role. In order to develop creative thinking, it is necessary to have effects to evoke and form the qualities and attributes of creative personality for students, to stimulate and spark the imagination, and overcome the ruts in thinking to create the necessary conditions to develop creative thinking[2]. The creative thinking of primary school students is in the formative stage at the beginning and gradually perfected at the end of primary school. The change in the relationship between concrete, intuitive thinking and abstract thinking prevails at the end of primary school. The process of classification, comparison, generalization, and inference takes place more often. This creates basic advantages for teachers in designing and organizing teaching activities

based on problem solving, thereby aiming to develop students' creative thinking ability. Learning through playing is an approach to education in which students interact, experience, explore and solve problems in a fun learning environment. Teachers connect learning goals with activities to promote student participation and autonomy, thereby developing their qualities and competencies. The word "Play" is not just games or activities, but is understood in the sense of discovery and problem-solving. Through Learning through playing, students will become independent, self-directed, socially engaged, creative, adaptable to all situations and have good problem-solving abilities. Learning through playing will create opportunities for learners to develop comprehensively in cognitive, creative thinking, emotional, social and physical skills. Many researchers also point out the role of learning through playing in the development of cognitive thinking as well as creative thinking in primary school students. Playing contributes to the development of foundational skills and knowledge, including supporting the learning of reading, writing, math and science. Playing leads to better results in the cognitive-language and in the social-emotional domains. Playing also affects originality of thought, flexibility in association, empathy associated with cooperative behavior, and social skills. Therefore, learning through playing is an approach with many advantages in creating opportunities for learners to practice and develop themselves. Learning through playing is implemented in association with five basic characteristics: pleasure, meaningfulness, active participation, social interaction, and opportunities for experimentation. Playing is always influenced by factors of learning environment, friends, available materials[3]. Learning through playing has 3 basic types: free play, guided play and game.

- Free play is also important for learning problem solving skills. “Learners can try to solve a problem or find a solution by themselves during playing. They should manage to express their own way of thinking. Those skills develop when a child is playing independently”.
- Guided play combines the best elements of free play and direct instruction: child autonomy and adult expertise. It provides an optimal medium for delivering educational content in ways that are enjoyable and that allow for genuine child agency, while constraining children's activities to facilitate learning.
- Game-based learning occurs when teachers use competitive, interactive, and entertaining activities to encourage students to engage in classroom learning.

They involve elements that are engaging and competitive that offer students immediate rewards[4].

In the teaching process, the most significant resource is the teachers and the learners, diversity and positive interaction in the classroom is an opportunity for creativity to absorb knowledge. Learning through playing is an educational approach that can be exploited and used in teaching many subjects and educational activities in primary schools. This approach creates opportunities for primary students to engage in learning activities that are intuitive, fun, and engaging. Learners' creativity can be realized through all three types of play with diverse forms, suitable for the characteristics of the lesson as well as the student. Suggestions on how to develop students' creative thinking with the approach of learning through playing proposed by the authors above are considered as a teaching "strategy" for teachers in teaching and developing creative thinking skills and problem-solving skills for students.

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